

Creating Women Leaders Through LSRW Skills in Connection with Communication & Psychological Aspects (LSRW - Listening, Speaking, Reading & Writing)

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Abstract

Women face multiple problems globally. Education which develops apt Communication and Psychological skills in both sexes, make men and women socially, economically, intellectually and morally useful and fit. This study focuses on the development of leadership skills in women with good communication and psychological aspects, so that they could handle their problems smoothly and bring peace and harmony to the family and the society. This results in the world's success at all levels steered by men and women.

Introduction

Women for over thousand years have been marginalized. Due to lack of education, they were silent and invisible in the public arena. In meeting the challenges of women and girl children, Communication is one of the most important ingredients and the next is their Psychological behaviour. The four important skills namely Listening, Speaking, Reading & Writing not only help to develop one's own communication, but also the personality development. Through education, we can impart these four skills and thereby create women leaders. There is a famous Chinese saying "If you want to plan for a year, Plant" Wheat, if you wish to plan for 10 years, grow Tree, but if you plan for 100 years, educate Women, highlighting the role of women and women's education in the development.

Women in the Society

The status of women is considered secondary in the society. It affects at every levels of their existence before birth, after birth, during childhood, in youth, after marriage and also at the old age. Women are imposed with restrictions and customs. The great Greek

Philosopher Plato was the first who advocated a state controlled system of compulsory education for both sexes. To him, the function of education was to make a man and woman socially, economically, intellectually and politically useful and fit. Hence Education is the essential process through which women are gaining Confidence, Self-esteem and the Skills to equip themselves and also blooming as leaders. Through education women can attain a good leadership quality which consists of exemplary communication and psychological skills.

Leaders

A person who influences another person towards success is known as a Leader. A leader is one who leads others. As a strategy to improve leadership skills, active listening, speaking, reading and writing can encourage stronger communication and personality. These skills are the great necessity in today's competitive world. At this juncture, 3 Women Leaders in various capacities are taken for models.

Helen Keller (1887 – 1968), Courageous Woman

Helen was born in Tuscumbia, Alabama on June 27, 1880. In 1882, she was stricken by an illness that left her blind and deaf. She always recalled that the most important day she can remember in her life; it was the day when Annie Sullivan, a 20-year-old graduate of the Perkins School for the Blind, came to be her teacher. Beginning in 1887, Keller's teacher, Anne Sullivan helped her make tremendous progress with her ability to communicate. In 1900, she entered Radcliffe College and graduated from there cum laude in 1904. Throughout these years, Annie Sullivan laboriously spelled books and lectures into her pupil's hand. She thus became the first deaf – blind person to graduate from college. During her lifetime, she received many honours in recognition of her accomplishments. In his eulogy at her funeral, Senator Lister Hill said of her, "she will live on, one of the few, immortal names not born to die". Her spirit will endure as long as man can read and stories can be told of the woman who showed the world there are no boundaries to courage and faith.

Marie Curie (1867 – 1934), Discovered Radium

Dr. Marie Curie is best known as the discoverer of the radioactive elements Polonium and Radium. She is the first person to win two Nobel prizes, in 1901 with the Nobel Prize in Physics and in 1911 Nobel Prize in Chemistry. Together with her husband, Pierre, she discovered two new elements and studied the x-rays they emitted. She found that the harmful properties of x-rays were able to kill tumors.

Medha Patkar (1954-till now alive) Indian Social Activist

Medha Patkar was born as Medha Khanolkar on 1st December, 1954 in Mumbai. She got her MA in social work from Tata Institute of Social Science. She is an Indian Social Activist, working on various crucial political and economical issues raised by Tribals, Dalits, Farmers, Labourers and Women facing injustice in India. Patkar is the founder member of the 32 years old peoples movement called Narmada Bachao Andolan (NBA) in three States: Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra and Gujarat. She is also one of the founders of the National Alliance of Peoples Movements (NAPM), an alliance of hundreds of progressive peoples organizations. In addition to the above, Patkar was a commissioner of the World commission on Dams, Which did a thorough research on the environmental, social, political and economic aspects and impacts of the development of large dams globally and their alternatives.

LSRW Skills

LSRW skills have a great impact on the success of an individual and the society. Through proper education, one can be master over the four communication skills, listening, Speaking, Reading & Writing and thereby efficient in language and maintain a personality which attracts others. Healthy communication between leaders and team members establishes a foundation for trust. A recent poll of U.S workers revealed that 91 percent of employers identified “communication issues” as a pain point with their bosses. So to familiarize with each skill, we can see each skills in detail.

Listening

We can see listening skills in terms of language skills and also in terms of personality concept. Dalai Lama said, When you speak, you repeat what you know, When you listen, you learn something new. In terms of language skills, this makes us to listen the sounds of that particular language. This would help them with the right pronunciation of words. The most important communication skills for leaders is the ability to listen.

In terms of personality skills, it includes listening for the message, listening for any emotions behind the message and considering relevant questions about the message. It includes listening without prejudgment, reflecting the other person’s feelings with appropriate statements. When the team members know that they will be heard, they are more apt to openly share their ideas and provide honest feedback. This in turn drives the team member’s positive outcomes including innovation, productivity and profitability.

Speaking

In terms of language skills, this skill could be improved by understanding para-linguistic attributes such as voice quality, volume and tone, voice modulation, articulation and pronunciation. This could also be further enhanced with the help of debates and discussions.

In terms of personality skills, through speaking we also communicate our psychological thinking and knowledge with others. We express our ideas and know others ideas as well. If a leaders can explain his / herself in the fewest possible number of words, he / she is winning.

Reading

In terms of language skills, it helps to develop language intuition in the corrected form. Then the brain imitates them, producing similar sentences to express the desired meaning. Using skimming or scanning technique to read quickly and deeply and copy the message into our brain.

In terms of personality skills, Reading makes a leader a more adept and articulate communicator. Reading increases verbal intelligence. Reading makes one a better thinker. As a leader, one needs a lot of general information to maintain perspective and seize opportunities. This is the most efficient way to acquire information and stay updated on the topics.

Writing

Anais Nin, a French Cuban Novelist said, “We write to taste life twice, in the moment and in retrospect”. Good writing skills allow you to communicate your message with clarity and ease to reach a far audience than through face –to-face or telephone conversations. Although majority of our interaction is carried out verbally or non-verbally, our behavioral thinking and ideas are authorized only through writing. A woman with a very good personality leads the others to have the same by her writings as well.

Benefits of LSRW Skills

By practicing LSRW skills, we can gain many leadership qualities. A few of them are furnished below:

- By listening, our relationship with people will be more harmonious.
- Listening to language helps us to pronounce correctly.
- By speaking we gain confidence and become more popular.
- Speaking in public, we inspire others to improve their communication skills.
- Writing skills make the difference between good and bad more authentically.
- Good writing preserves the knowledge for the future generation.
- By reading we gain vocabulary and knowledge.
- Reading helps us to free ourselves from stress and increase our concentration power and analytical thinking capacity.

Conclusion

With these four skills (LSRW), the communication skills and a adorable personality. Women can be assured of developing confidence and lead the society in success.

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